

High-Power Ultrafast LaSers using tapered double-clad fibre

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Introduction and background

The development and application of innovative photonics-based manufacturing solutions will open new ways of producing more goods with fewer raw materials, less energy and less waste. The challenge is to develop systems which deliver improved accuracy, power and control and which will enable the next generation of manufacturing in a range of industrial sectors.

Already, ultrafast lasers with pulse durations in the femtosecond and picosecond range play a central role in many industrial processes. The ability of these lasers for high-quality, virtually athermal material processing, coupled with advances in laser technology, process development, beam handling, and delivery, have opened the door for numerous advanced scientific and industrial applications.

However, to achieve significant growth in uptake of these lasers, several critical steps remain that require significant efforts in laser research and development towards high-average-power ultrafast lasers, including beam handling and delivery to take full advantage of the potential processing speed.

The dramatic rise in output power from fibre sources over the past decade, using cladding-pumped fibre architectures, has led to a range of fibre-based devices with outstanding performance in terms of output power, beam quality, overall efficiency, and flexibility in operating wavelength and radiation format. This success is largely due to the fibre's geometry, which provides considerable resilience to the effects of heat generation in the core and facilitates highly efficient conversion from relatively low-brightness diode pump radiation to high-brightness laser output.

The PULSE project will harness the unique capabilities of tapered double-clad fibre (T-DCF) amplifiers to realise the prospect of even higher power with excellent beam properties in a very space-effective format and at production costs no more than normal fibres. This will mean the cost per watt can meet the requirements for rapid industrial uptake and deliver strong investment returns to industry from increased processing speed and precision.

A breakthrough concept in high-power industrial lasers

Laser technology continues to have an almost unlimited number of applications. Following widespread developments using continuous-wave lasers, breakthroughs in high-power short-pulsed lasers were recently recognised by the Nobel Prize in Physics 2018 to Gérard Mourou and Donna Strickland for their method of generating high-intensity, ultra-short optical pulses.

Although, a relatively short time ago, the femtosecond laser was a tool consigned to the laboratory; now these systems have developed the reliability necessary for use in industry. Ultrafast pulsed lasers have seen exponential growth with the number of filed patents increasing five-fold from about 100 to 500 per year (Mottay, 2013). Several advanced niche applications have benefited from fs-laser processing including in photonics (Misawa and Juodkakis, 2006), microelectronics (Rizvi, Karnakis and Gower, 2001), MEMS (Bellouard, 2011) and many other markets.

The outstanding characteristics of fibre lasers compared to disc lasers, including compactness, robustness, efficiency, ease of thermal management, reliable beam quality and significantly lower production and maintenance costs make fibre-based approaches highly appealing for ultrafast, ps and fs high-power kW-level laser development.

Today's high-average-power fibre lasers generally consist of a relatively low-power master oscillator, or seed laser, and power amplifier scheme. However, despite the attractive characteristics of fibre lasers, several problems arise when power scaling. The most significant are thermal lensing and material resistance, non-linear effects such as stimulated Raman scattering, stimulated Brillouin scattering, mode instabilities and poor output beam quality.

Tapered double-clad fibre lasers (T-DCF) overcome these fundamental technological challenges and provide significant production cost advantage with respect to disc and rod-type fibres, while also satisfying the requirements for high-power short-pulse applications.

Tapered double-clad fibre lasers

T-DCF is a solid-type fibre whose outer and inner claddings and core diameters vary smoothly with its length (Figure 1). This geometric structure provides significant technological benefits for common problems arising with power scaling. The core at the narrow side of the T-DCF only supports propagation of the fundamental mode, whereas at its wide end the core can guide many modes.

Experimental results have shown that light launched into the narrow end of a T-DCF

Tapered fiber provides higher conversion efficiency and elevated non-linearity threshold

Figure 1: Illustration of active tapered double-clad fibre.

propagates in a wide core without any changes to the mode content (Kerttula *et al.*, 2013). As a result, at the wide end of the T-DCF, the light coupling-out remained in fundamental mode with excellent beam quality. Thus, tapered fibre offers a unique and easy way to implement fundamental mode propagation and amplification in a multimode fibre.

The large core diameter of T-DCF already achieved record pulse energy values of 280µJ and 5MW of peak power (Filippov *et al.*, 2016) from a single channel without non-linear distortions.

Project objectives

The PULSE project aims to develop and validate a novel ultra-short pulse fibre laser system based on the unique advantages of high-power tapered fibre amplifiers, overcoming the classical difficulties of high-power ultrashort pulse generation in fibres and demonstrating the benefits of tailored optics for high-power 3D laser material processing. Using all-fibre coherent beam combining and an ultrafast polygon scanner, we will demonstrate new speed and precision possibilities for picosecond and femtosecond laser processing in dissimilar metal fusion, precision micro-textured mould and hard material cutting.

To address the opportunities for faster, more precise and non-thermal laser manufacturing PULSE will develop a T-DCF laser delivering up to an astonishing 2.5kW with pulse durations as short as 100fs and pulse repetition rates up to 1GHz. A complete laser processing system capable of handling high-power ultrashort pulses with scanning speeds up to 1.5km/s and fibre integrated optics to provide spot sizes down to 10µm. The technology is much faster and will enable 3D laser processing across a range of industries at costs which can underpin high return on investment decisions.

PULSE will develop and demonstrate new faster laser processing of up to 100m/s with an accuracy of better than 10µm in the cutting of boron steel (Figure 2), the hardest known steel, micro-texturing of steel moulds and joining of dissimilar metals, aluminium and copper (Figure 3), which will take advantage of the lower heat-induced deformation of ultrashort pulses. Laser radiation wavelength will be 1,040nm, and pulse energies from 2.5–250µJ delivered via specifically designed solid-core fibre (CeramOptec).

By designing highly stable seed lasers (Tampere University and AIPT), which determine the properties of the high-power

beams and fast control systems, we will provide pulse duration and repetition rate flexibility to optimising pulse and delivery parameters to meet the needs of these and many other applications.

The system control aspects for high-power ultrafast lasers will be fully addressed, including pulse on demand, tunable pulse duration and tunable repetition rate. A high-speed polygon scanner developed by Mittweida University and marketed by spin-out Moewe, together with a 5-Axis fully 3D capable fast kinematic system (Lunovu), will enable precise and efficient processing of 3D objects which will be demonstrated in injection mould micro-structuring for car parts (Figure 4).

Using novel fibre facet-integrated micro-optics produced using nano-imprinted lithography with ultra-pure high damage threshold materials (FORTH and Nanotypos), PULSE will enable the compact connection of multiple T-DCF channels, 10µm scale laser ablation for materials processing and surface patterning. Beam shaping using diffractive optical elements will also be developed with the polygon scanner to shape the beam focus, enabling the effective voxel depth to be increased by a factor of four, and thus enabling similar increases in 3D processing by reducing focusing time and re-focussing operations.

Furthermore, PULSE aims to actively disseminate the potential benefits of high-power laser processing to industrial stakeholders likely to benefit from the advances in laser processing technology (Modus). A programme of specific workshops will help encourage and stimulate adoption of the technology, including the investment case parameters which PULSE will make more attractive through lower than current technology costs.

Figure 2: Laser cutting of boron steel for vehicle chassis.

Figure 3: Illustration of the Cu tube Al sheet welding process.

Figure 4: Interior detail of 334 project (500X FIAT as upper picture). Detail of interior photoetched textures for low gloss plastic.

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PROJECT SUMMARY

By harnessing the unique characteristics of tapered double-clad fibre, PULSE will develop a world record power 2.5kW industrial laser providing picosecond to femtoseconds pulses at repetition rates up to 1GHz with excellent beam quality. Demonstration of 3D material processing with ultimate precision and speed in the EU automotive and renewables sectors at competitive costs will advance industrial laser production technologies.

PROJECT LEAD PROFILE

Regina Gumenyuk was awarded two MSc degrees in 2008 from Lappeenranta University and St.Petersburg State University and in 2014 a PhD from Tampere University. Her doctorate explored novel gain materials now used in mode-locked fibre lasers. Her pioneering research is high-power-ultrafast pulsed fibre laser fabrication and amplification. She coordinates two Horizon 2020 projects and has authored more than 55 peer-reviewed publications.

PROJECT PARTNERS

Dr Gumenyuk has assembled the PULSE consortium from Tampere University and spin-out Ampliconix, the world leaders in, and originators of, the core ideas around high-power pulsed T-DCF lasers. The consortium from six EU countries comprises eight companies, a Greek research institute and high-quality UK and German universities. It brings together a team with state-of-the-art technologies and application expertise.

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